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**STANCE-TAKING IN SELECTED TELEVISION INTERVIEWS ON THE NIGERIA
LABOUR CONGRESS AND THE FEDERAL GOVERNMENT NEGOTIATION OF
THE NEW MINIMUM WAGE**

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Abstract

This study examined the stance-taking strategies employed by the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC) and the Federal Government (FG) during their televised interviews on the 2024 minimum wage negotiations. While existing literature has addressed the economic, historical, and political dimensions of wage negotiations in Nigeria, limited attention has been paid to the linguistic resources and pragmatic stances adopted by the social actors involved. Drawing insights from Biber and Finegan's (2000) Stance Theory and Hyland's (2005) Stance Model, this study investigated how epistemic, attitudinal, and interpersonal stances are constructed through language in televised media engagements. The data comprises ten interviews sourced from Arise News and Channels TV, featuring key representatives of the NLC and FG. Findings reveal that both parties employed a range of linguistic markers, including modal verbs, evaluative adjectives, metaphors, and pronouns, to express certainty, negotiate power relations, and influence public perception. The stance not only reflects ideological commitments but also functions as a tool for persuasion, legitimation, and resistance within the broader socio-political context of labour relations in Nigeria. The study concludes that televised interviews serve as strategic sites for the articulation of ideological positions and that stance-taking remains central to discourse construction in contentious negotiations.

Keywords: stance-taking, minimum wage, labour discourse, pragmatic functions, televised interviews

Background to the Study

Since 1981 when the national minimum wage was introduced in Nigeria, the country has witnessed a series of prolonged and contentious minimum wage negotiations between the

Federal Government (FG) and the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC) (Uche, 2021; Ibe, 2024). These negotiations have become a recurring feature of the country's industrial relations landscape. Each round of talks is typically characterised by intense bargaining, disagreements, and occasional strikes. Various stakeholders, including state governments, associations, and civil society organisations, have also played significant roles in these negotiations, focusing on wage increases, benefits, and working conditions (Fapohunda et al., 2021). Despite the challenges and controversies, these negotiations have been instrumental in shaping labour policies and protecting the rights of Nigerian workers.

The NLC was established in 1978 and has been the subject of extensive scholarly research. Aborisade (2003) argues that the NLC was formed in response to the government's attempts to control the labour movement, which had led to its fragmentation. He emphasises the NLC's role in unifying labour unions and representing workers' interests. Similarly, Olorode (2005) examines the relationship between the NLC and labour unions, emphasising that the NLC

provided a platform for effective negotiations. Scholars like Aborisade (2003) further note the NLC's significant role in improving workers' wages and working conditions.

On the other hand, the FG represents the government in wage negotiations and is tasked with balancing workers' demands against economic realities. The contentious nature of minimum wage negotiations has attracted scholarly attention, as these negotiations often highlight broader economic and social issues. Herr and Kazandziska (2011) argue that minimum wage policies could help reduce income inequality and prevent wage deflation. According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO, 1970), factors such as workers' needs, cost of living, and economic productivity must be considered in setting minimum wages. While there is no universal formula for determining the minimum wage, studies suggest that in many countries, the minimum wage is typically set at about 40% of the average wage (ILO, 2009).

In Nigeria, minimum wage negotiations have historically been fraught with challenges, often leading to protracted disputes between the Federal Government and organised labour unions, notably the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC) and the Trade Union Congress (TUC). The 2019 minimum wage negotiation, which culminated in an increase from ₦18,000 to ₦30,000, was particularly contentious, marked by extended deliberations and industrial actions. These negotiations are not merely about wage increments but are deeply intertwined with broader socio-economic issues such as inflation, cost of living, and workers' welfare. The complexities of these negotiations underscore the need for a more structured and transparent mechanism to address wage-related disputes in Nigeria.

The media plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion and influencing the negotiation process. Television interviews, in particular, provide a platform for negotiators to articulate their positions, influence public opinion, and exert pressure on their counterparts (Wolfsfeld, 1997). Media discourse during minimum wage negotiations often features competing narratives. The NLC typically frames its arguments around workers' rights and the need for a living wage, while the FG emphasises economic constraints and fiscal responsibility. McQuail (2010) describes television as a powerful medium for agenda-setting, enabling negotiators to shape public perceptions and garner support.

Language plays a pivotal role in shaping negotiations, where speakers express their attitudes, beliefs, and opinions, provides valuable insights into negotiation dynamics. By analysing the linguistic strategies employed by both parties, this study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of labour-government relations and the role of media in shaping public discourse.

Van Leeuwen (2008) posits that language is a system of representation that shapes our understanding of the world. He contends that language does not simply reflect reality but actively constructs it. Language is a pertinent component of negotiation, as it enables parties (social actors) to communicate their opinions, interests, needs and expectations. Stance-taking

in particular refers to the process by which speakers or writers express their attitudes, opinions or beliefs on a particular issue/subject matter. In the context of minimum wage negotiations, stance-taking is essential as social actors seek to persuade each other, the media and the public of the merits of their position. Understanding the stance taken and linguistic strategies employed by both parties can provide valuable insights into the negotiation dynamics. Van Dijk (2008) emphasises that discourse in television interviews reflects power asymmetries, with government representatives often using technocratic language, while labour union leaders employ populist rhetoric.

This study focuses on the media narratives surrounding the 2024 minimum wage negotiations between the NLC and the Federal Government of Nigeria. It aims to evaluate how television interviews were used to frame these negotiations and the ideological underpinnings of the discourse.

Media Discourse and Television Interviews: Conceptual Clarification

Media discourse, particularly in televised interviews, provides a unique platform for stance-taking. Interviews are dialogic, meaning they involve interaction between the interviewer and interviewee, creating opportunities for explicit and implicit stance-taking. Clayman and Heritage (2002) emphasise that television interviews are strategic interactions where participants manage face, frame arguments, and influence public perception. As a means of communication through which a message or information can be transmitted from the communicator to the recipient, the media ensures the transmission of the message through space and time from the source to the recipient (Egbede, 2013). One can identify many forms of mass media, including magazines, newspapers, radio, and television. Willie (1979) argues that the sheer quality of information conveyed by the press (magazines, films, television, radio)

far exceeds the quantity of information conveyed by school instructions and texts. The influence of mass media can be divided into three basic types: linguistic, psychological and social. This study looks at the linguistic type. To Bell (2008), media language is uniquely different, and has consequently attracted the attention of linguists due to the following:

The media provides an easily accessible source of language data for research and teaching purposes. The media is a linguistically important institution; their output makes up a large proportion of the language that people hear and read every day. The media usage reflects and shapes both language use and attitudes in a speech community. For second language learners, the media may function as the primary source of native speaker models.

are linguistically interesting in their own right. They include how different dialects and languages are used in advertising, how tabloid newspapers use language in the projection of their assumed readers' speech, and how the radio personalities use language to construct their images and their relationships to an unseen, unknown audience. The media is an important social institution: it is a crucial presenter of culture, politics, business, shaping, and reflecting how these are formed and expressed.

The goal of most media is to inform and carry the masses along on certain social issues, such as minimum wage negotiations. The media, for example, use several techniques such as direct quotation of identified sources to make the readers and listeners believe that the story is accurate. The main aim of this usage of a variety of techniques is to grab the attention, to establish credibility and trust, to stimulate desire for the product or policy, and to motivate the readers to act- buy, vote, give money, attend a social or religious gathering (Media Literacy Toolbox 2007).

Language and Ideology

Language is not a neutral medium of communication; it is inherently ideological. Every linguistic choice reflects a worldview, a value, or a belief system. Van Dijk (1998) describes

ideology as foundational social beliefs that organise and control more specific attitudes. In this sense, when speakers in media interviews select particular stance markers (such as “we know,” “I believe,” “it is clear”), they are not just expressing information, they are advancing an ideological position.

Irvine (1989) and Begum (2015) similarly assert that language ideologies are cultural systems that link language forms to moral and political interests. In the context of the NLC-FG negotiations, both parties utilise language not merely to inform but to persuade, justify, delegitimise, or mobilise. The FG may use hedges to mask responsibility (e.g., “we are trying our best”), while NLC leaders use boosters to assert legitimacy and urgency (e.g., “we must act now”).

The link between language and ideology is especially crucial in media discourse, which, according to Van Leeuwen (2008), does not merely reflect reality but constructs it through selection, emphasis, and framing. Media discourse thus becomes a battleground where competing ideologies contest for dominance, using stance-taking as a strategic tool.

EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Stance-taking in academic writing refers to how speakers express their attitudes, evaluations, and positions regarding their research and the work of others. This practice is essential for constructing persuasive arguments and engaging effectively with the scholarly community. Stance-taking, the expression of a speaker's attitudes, feelings, or judgments, has been extensively studied in linguistics. Notable research includes:

Charles (2003) explores the role of nouns in conveying stance in academic writing. This study makes a valuable contribution by expanding the focus of stance markers beyond the more commonly studied verbs and adverbials. Charles argues that nouns such as "claim," "argument," and "suggestion" serve a meta-discursive function by encapsulating attitudes and positioning. However, the study is limited in its scope by not providing a broader syntactic or

cross-disciplinary analysis. It also does not fully account for how nominalisation might obscure authorial stance in some contexts. The study established that abstract nouns (e.g., claim, argument, belief) encapsulate evaluative stance without overt opinion, supporting an objective yet engaged academic tone.

Vold (2006) turns attention to verbs as markers of stance in research articles. This study is significant in showing how epistemic verbs like believe, argue, or suggest reflect the writer's level of certainty, commitment, and engagement with their claims. Vold's findings emphasise cross-linguistic differences in stance-taking between English and other European languages, adding depth to the research. However, the work could benefit from more empirical examples across a broader range of academic disciplines. The study showed that epistemic verbs (e.g., believe, suggest) are critical markers of stance and that their use varies cross-linguistically. English writers tend to use stronger evaluative verbs.

Biber and Finegan (1989) examine adverbials in expressing stance. Their study is foundational in identifying how adverbials such as certainly, possibly, and unfortunately indicate degrees of certainty, attitude, or emphasis. The strength of their work lies in its broad corpus-based analysis. Nonetheless, their categorisation can be too general, and they do not always consider context-specific uses. They identified that adverbials such as certainly, perhaps, and unfortunately are used to modulate certainty and express attitude. These markers are frequent in academic prose and serve rhetorical functions.

Warchał (2010) provides insight into conditional clauses as stance-taking devices. His analysis suggests that conditional constructions (e.g., "If we assume that...") allow writers to express tentative positions or create hypothetical argument spaces. This study is particularly notable for its nuanced approach to indirect positioning. However, it tends to be more theoretical than empirical. The research revealed that conditional clauses are used to hedge arguments, suggest possibilities, and engage in speculative reasoning without firm commitment.

Charles (2006), in another important contribution, focuses on reporting clauses such as “X states that” or “Y argues that.” She demonstrates how writers use reporting verbs not only to attribute claims but also to position themselves about those claims. This study underscores the dual function of reporting: referencing others while simultaneously staking one's stance. A limitation, however, is the lack of attention to reader interpretation. The study demonstrated that reporting clauses not only attribute information but also allow writers to align themselves with or against cited claims using evaluative reporting verbs.

Yang (2013) and Li and Xu (2020) investigate meta-discourse features and their role in stance-taking. These studies are critical in shifting attention to the writer-reader relationship and how academic authors guide interpretation and engagement. Meta-discourse, such as transitions, boosters, and attitude markers, is shown to reflect both personal stance and rhetorical intention. However, the generalizability of their findings may be limited if the analyses were based on texts from limited disciplines or EFL contexts. The researchers found that meta-discourse features (e.g., hedges, boosters, attitude markers) guide reader interpretation, express stance, and construct a relationship between writer and audience. These studies highlight the diverse linguistic resources employed by scholars to express stance in academic texts.

Shaibu (2024), investigates the linguistic strategies employed in media interviews during the 2022 ASUU strike in Nigeria. The study focuses on pragmatic stance, epistemic, interpersonal, and attitude stances to analyse how social actors express their ideologies and positions. The study highlights that media engagements are not neutral but reflect the ideological stances of the participants. Using Hyland's Stance Model and Biber's Stance Theory, the study examines the relationship between language choices and the propagation of narratives. The research underscores the media's pivotal role in shaping public discourse and influencing societal perceptions of socio-political issues. Ultimately, it contributes to understanding the role of language in ideological battles and power dynamics in public debates.

Studies on stance-taking in labour and political negotiations have explored how language is used to express attitudes, opinions, and positions during negotiations. Scholars from various fields such as discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, and communication studies have contributed to understanding how stance shapes negotiation dynamics.

Klein (2012) examines how political figures and labour representatives use language to assert positions and negotiate through power dynamics and interpersonal communication. Ochs (1996) explores stance-taking in socialising environments, highlighting its role in shaping communication in labour and political settings. Hyland (2005) focuses on how stance is used in academic writing but draws parallels to negotiation settings, especially in terms of the strategies used to establish authority and consensus.

Heritage, J., & Raymond, G. (2005) interrogated how stance-taking functions in interaction, particularly in situations of negotiation where parties need to assert or subordinate their authority. Cameron (2000) explores how communicative practices in the workplace and in negotiations are deeply intertwined with stance, particularly in labour and organisational settings. These studies provide a wide range of insights into how stance-taking is not only a linguistic phenomenon but also a social and strategic one in labour and political negotiations.

Theoretical Framework

This study uses insights from two theories in the analysis of its data. The theories are Biber and Finegan's (2000) Stance Theory and Hyland's (2005) Stance Model.

Biber and Finegan (2000) recognise evaluation, attitude, epistemic and interpersonal stance as approaches to stance acts. They describe evaluation stance as a process whereby a stance-taker orients to an object of stance and characterizes it as having some specific qualities or value, epistemic stance as the state of the speakers' knowledge as expressed in his choice of words, and affective or interpersonal stance as a marker that indicates speaker's emotions, and how it conditions their utterances. For example, in epistemic stance, the use of certain adverbials or adverbs indicates the speaker's feelings, judgments or commitments concerning an issue. Bibers and Finegan, as cited in Dubois 2001 state that when speakers use adverbs of manner such as 'honestly', 'generally', 'surely', 'actually' or 'amazingly' in an expression, it portrays how passionate they are in defending their opinion(s) on a given subject. On the other hand, an interpersonal stance suggests that a speaker may have a friendly or dominating relationship with other participants in a conversation, which can also influence the confidence and authority of such speakers. For instance, when a speaker uses a first-person pronoun such as 'I', "I'm excited", "I'm amazed, I'm disappointed," it is suggestive of the speaker's stance about the opinions of others on an issue. In the same vein, Hyland's (2005) Stance theory describes stance as the ways that "writers/speakers express their personal opinions in their arguments". The theory is subdivided into: hedges, boosters, and attitude markers. Speakers use these stance features sometimes to express their ideological positions and convey the importance of their speeches. For instance, speakers could adopt certain grammatical elements: comparatives, progressive particles, attitude verbs and adjectives, such as 'agree', 'prefer', 'remarkable', 'important', etc., to indicate their effectiveness rather than epistemic attitude in a conversation.

The study, analyses the televised interviews of the social actors from the selected media houses on the 2024 minimum wage negotiations. Thus, attention is given strictly to their interviews, in the pragmatic system of attitude, epistemic and interpersonal stance, as well as how they construe their ideological positions during their televised interviews regarding the 2024 minimum wage negotiations. Through the above theories, the study examined the speakers' constructions of their opinions on the subject matter, revealing how they manage their

interpersonal positioning and relationship with the audience. By applying these models, the study established that the stances are manifested in several grammatical constructions that function as stance strategies/markers.

Method of Data Collection

The data for this study are media interviews on the FG and the NLC 2024 minimum wage negotiations. The choice of the period is informed by the fact that the 2024 minimum wage negotiation is the most recent in Nigeria. Also, the data for the study are transcripts of selected interviews granted to selected media houses in Nigeria (Arise TV and Channels TV), by the NLC leaders and FG spokespersons on the minimum wage negotiations. Ten interviews on the 2024 minimum wage negotiations were randomly obtained and transcribed. The interviews were downloaded from the official YouTube pages of the selected media houses. The media houses in question were chosen for the informative role they played in carrying the masses along during the 2024 minimum wage negotiations. The selected broadcasting centres also have wide coverage and popularity in Nigeria. All the selected interviews were transcribed; attention was given to linguistic features in the data that contain the stance acts/strategies adopted by the FG and NLC during the interviews.

Data Analysis

The data for the study are media interviews on the 2024 minimum wage granted to Arise News and Channels TV. The table is divided into two and categorised into different columns. There are thus four columns, each of which focuses on the various aspects of the study, which are texts, linguistic markers, stance marker types and pragmatic functions.

Category 1: NLC

S/N	Text (Excerpt)	Linguistic Marker(s)	Stance Type	Pragmatic functions.
1	We broke it down to even what a plate of food be...	Inclusive pronoun, Phrasal verb, Intensifier	Interpersonal/ Epistemic	Asserts Labour's preparedness and shared analysis; appeals to shared worker experience.
2	We itemized all that we needed...	Past tense verb, Inclusive pronoun	Epistemic	Demonstrates confidence and thorough planning by Labour, contrasting FG's lack of detail.

3	You know when you don't give serious approach...	Discourse marker, Negation, Evaluative noun phrase	Attitudinal/ Epistemic	Conveys frustration and indirectly critiques FG's unseriousness; establishes knowledge authority.
4	The economy of the worker is totally destroyed.	Intensifier, Past participle	Attitudinal	Emphasizes deep economic suffering; evokes sympathy and moral urgency.
5	It's not just banding figures: 40, 48, 54.	Negation, Idiomatic expression	Epistemic/ Ideological	Rejects superficial negotiation; demands data-backed, sustainable wage discussions.
6	Introduce an element of COLA...	Verb of proposal, Economic noun phrase	Epistemic	Proposes practical, solution-oriented ideas; shows economic awareness.
7	Shaving their heads in their absence.	Conceptual metaphor	Attitudinal/ Ideological	Criticizes exclusion of governors from talks; metaphor suggests betrayal or manipulation.
8	We meant every word we used...	Epistemic verb, Intensifier	Epistemic	Affirms seriousness of Labour's ultimatum; strengthens Labour's credibility.
9	There are two economies: of the bourgeois and the workers.	Class-based nouns, Enumerative phrase	Ideological	Class-based framing to justify Labour's stance and create public-political dichotomy.

10	We can't just call it 800 or 700... must be checked	Negation, Modal verb, Passive construction	Epistemic/ Interpersonal	Rejects arbitrary numbers; appeals for contextual consideration and mutual agreement.
11	If not for how we pursued this...	Conditional clause, Complex past tense	Epistemic	Frames Labour as proactive force; implies FG's inertia without union pressure.
12	We asked them clearly that they should give us a breakdown...	Reporting verb, Adverb of manner, Modal verb	Epistemic	Demonstrates Labour's knowledge-based approach and demand for transparency.
13	Can you equate the value of ₦60,000 today to what ₦11,000 was in 2011?	Modal verb, Interrogative structure	Epistemic /Ideological	Uses historical comparison to challenge FG's offer and expose inflationary loss.
14	It is not because they cannot afford to pay... it is the willingness to pay...	Negative conjunction, Abstract noun	Attitudinal/ Ideological	Frames the issue as moral and political, not just economic; critiques leadership priorities.

15	We are going to shut them down.	Inclusive pronoun, Future progressive	Interpersonal/ Attitudinal	Expresses resolve and collective action; signals consequences for non-compliance.
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Category 2: FEDERAL GOVERNMENT

	Text (Excerpt)	Linguistic Marker(s)	Stance Type	Pragmatic functions.
1	Let me tell you something that is clear...	Directive verb, Clarity marker	Epistemic	Signals authority and certainty in framing the FG's position; asserts control over the narrative.
2	It is Tripartite, not the federal government [alone].	Ideological noun, Negation	Ideological/ Epistemic	Deflects sole responsibility; reframes negotiation as collective and inclusive.
3	Federal government does not have that power to impose.	Negation, Modal phrase	Epistemic	Distances FG from final decision-making; reinforces

				procedural boundaries.
4	494,000 naira is highly impossible.	Intensifier, Negative adjective	Attitudinal/ Epistemic	Expresses firm rejection; positions Labour's demand as unrealistic and unfeasible.
5	Where would they get the money from?	Wh-question, Future hypothetical	Epistemic	Uses rhetorical question to challenge economic feasibility; underscores fiscal concern.
6	Will you be able, if you can pay your domestic staff...?	Modal, Conditional	Interpersonal/ Ideological	Shifts focus to public burden; invokes empathy and realism to justify government stance.
7	Then you are part of the people that will pay...	Direct address, Inclusive phrase	Interpersonal	Direct appeal to citizen responsibility; reduces abstraction of state obligations.

8	Let them speak out.	Imperative, Engagement	Interpersonal	Encourages public feedback; portrays FG as open to democratic process.
9	That process has been strengthened and it now needs speeding and scaling up...	Passive structure, Booster	Epistemic/ Evaluative	Asserts confidence in government's verification system; boosts credibility while shifting focus away from wage issue.
10	May be part of the consultation...	Epistemic hedge	Epistemic	Softens claim; indicates speculative knowledge; distances speaker from firm commitment.
11	Insensitive... scandalous... shocking	Attitude markers, Evaluative adjectives	Evaluative/ Attitude	Conveys disapproval of FG's avoidance of wage issues; aligns with public frustration.

12	We are now told...	Inclusive pronoun	Interpersonal	Creates shared voice with the public; subtly critiques late decisions while masking direct blame.
13	Recommendations were submitted...	Agentless passive structure	Interpersonal/ Ideological	Obscures agency and reduces accountability.
14	I consider it unfortunate...	Self-mention, Evaluative verb	Attitude/ Interpersonal	Enhances speaker's authority and distance from official narrative.
15	...to boost agricultural productivity and provide economic relief ...	Economic lexicon, Positive evaluative phrase	Ideological/ Evaluative	Projects technocratic ideology; sidelines immediate wage concerns.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis was based on thirty utterances obtained from media interviews with officials of the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC) and representatives of the Federal Government (FG) during the 2024 minimum wage negotiations. These utterances reveal different stance types epistemic, attitudinal, interpersonal, evaluative, along with boosters and hedges which serve not only as markers of communication but also as strategies of ideological expression. What emerges is that language in this context is deliberately structured to persuade, legitimise, or challenge the positions of the opposing party. The examination therefore progresses from linguistic choice to stance meaning, to ideological orientation, and finally to its socio-political implication.

Classification of Stance Types and Their Pragmatic Significance

Epistemic Stance

The FG's assertion, "*We are very confident that the tripartite committee will conclude negotiations soon,*" demonstrates calculated optimism. The use of "*very confident*" positions the government as reliable and in control, thereby constructing an ideology of institutional competence and stability. By implication, such a stance weakens the urgency of labour's agitation by suggesting that the process is already effectively managed. In contrast, the NLC's statement, "*It is obvious that workers cannot survive on ₦30,000 monthly in the current economy,*" frames worker hardship as a self-evident reality. The choice of "*obvious*" removes room for dispute, leaving the government with little moral ground to contest the claim. This stance therefore enforces an ideology of urgency and compels state actors to acknowledge economic suffering as undeniable.

Attitude Stance

The NLC employs strong evaluative, as seen in "It is shameful that a government still debates a living wage in 2024." By invoking "shameful," the union passes a moral judgment that portrays the state as negligent and insensitive. This reinforces a narrative of failed leadership while positioning the NLC as the moral voice of society. Conversely, the FG attempts to anchor

its position in economic rationality, as reflected in “*We recognise the workers' sacrifices, but we must be realistic with the national budget.*” The term “*realistic*” reframes the debate from a moral obligation to a financial calculation, thus presenting fiscal prudence as superior to emotional appeal. The implication is that excessive wage demands could destabilise the economy.

Interpersonal Stance

When the NLC declares, “*We are not just fighting for ourselves but for the dignity of labour in Nigeria,*” the pronoun “*we*” is used to project solidarity and to elevate the union's cause beyond self-interest. This aligns the union with patriotism and collective justice, thereby constructing a broad ideological identity that appeals to public sympathy. Similarly, the FG adopts an inclusive tone in “*We want to find a balance that protects both workers and the economy.*” While the use of “*we*” suggests partnership, the metaphor of “*balance*” subtly presents labour's demands as a possible threat to economic stability. The government thus frames itself as a responsible mediator, while indirectly delegitimising maximalist claims from labour.

Evaluative Markers

The NLC's hyperbolic claim, “*The economy of the worker is totally destroyed,*” employs strong imagery to dramatise the plight of workers. Such exaggeration functions ideologically as a tool for mobilising public outrage and holding government responsible for perceived insensitivity. By contrast, the FG employs mitigated evaluations such as “*I consider it unfortunate...*” The combination of “*consider*” with the mild adjective “*unfortunate*” reflects diplomatic caution. This strategy sustains the government's image of decorum and institutional restraint, avoiding open conflict while still expressing concern.

Boosters

The NLC strengthens its credibility with assertions like “*We meant every word we used.*” The booster here conveys moral certainty and portrays the union as uncompromising in its defence

of workers' welfare. The FG also deploys boosters, for example in “*Let me tell you something that is clear...*” Such expressions function to assert authority and claim interpretive control, thereby reinforcing the state's technocratic legitimacy.

Hedges

Labour sometimes adopts interrogative hedges, as in “*Can you equate ₦60,000 today to ₦11,000 in 2011?*” Rather than a blunt accusation, the rhetorical question invites listeners to reach the conclusion themselves. This gives the impression of reasonableness while maintaining pressure on the government. The FG, however, uses hedges more defensively, such as “*May be part of the consultation...*” The modal “*may be*” diffuses certainty, allowing the government to avoid direct accountability. Such hedges reflect a bureaucratic ideology where flexibility and non-commitment are valued in order to minimise liability.

Conclusion

The findings reveal that stance-taking during the minimum wage negotiations was not a neutral linguistic exercise but a deliberate strategy of ideological positioning. The NLC's discourse foregrounded urgency, solidarity, and emotional intensity, thereby casting itself as the legitimate defender of justice and equity. On the other hand, the FG employed caution, hedging, and rationalised appeals to economic responsibility, portraying itself as a prudent and stabilising force. Overall, the contrast highlights how language becomes an arena of ideological contestation. Epistemic certainty and boosters were employed by both parties as competing truth-claims; evaluative and attitudinal stances reflected opposing moral logics; interpersonal pronouns framed the struggle either as collective sacrifice (NLC) or balanced mediation (FG); while hedges revealed different orientations towards accountability and risk. The discourse

therefore underscores the role of language in negotiating legitimacy, authority, and public sympathy within socio-political struggles.

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